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Abstract	The Data Management Plan (final) provides information on data management and personal data protection principles that were followed in the course of the
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	<p>project and will be followed after its completion. It explains how partners managed their data and how they ensured compliance with legal and ethical requirements, while providing data in a FAIR manner. It also describes the approach with regards to intellectual property rights. This final DMP reflects how the partners implemented the initial strategy into managing practices at different points of the project lifecycle, ensuring consistency with the status of the project data catalogue (GeoNetwork).</p>
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CF	Climate and Forecast metadata conventions
CitSci	Citizen Science
CSVW	CSV on the Web (W3C standard)
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web (OGC standard)
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary (W3C standard)
DGA	Data Governance Act
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPA	Data Protection Authority
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EDC	Eclipse Data Connector
EEA	European Environment Agency
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA5	ECMWF Reanalysis v5
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable
FLC	Functional Landscape Connectivity
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GDIM	Green Deal Information Model
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IPT	Integrity, Provenance, Trust

ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LD	Linked Data
NIS	Network and Information Security Directive
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PROV	W3C Provenance Ontology
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index
STA	SensorThings API
TAPIS	Tables from APIs for Sensors (STApplus Explorer)
UI	User Interface
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WAI	Water Availability Index
WP	Work Package
WP29	Article 29 Working Party
WQI	Water Quality Index
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document represents the final Data Management Plan (DMP) for the AD4GD project. It provides the final information on the management and sharing of data that were generated, used and processed during the AD4GD project, with a particular focus on the pilot sites.

Throughout the project, partners primarily processed and produced non-personal data, thus placing particular focus on their alignment with FAIR principles, prioritizing the data's Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability. This is further highlighted by their Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Strategy, outlined in this document, which promotes open science. Where personal data was involved, partners adopted adequate measures to ensure it remains protected and confidential, without harming the innovation aspects of the project.

This document focuses on reporting the achievements in data management aspects in AD4GD through demonstrating that a GeoNetwork catalogue provides discoverability of all data in the project; the distribution aspects on the metadata in GeoNetwork ensures data access; and the tools for data semantics (e.g. Green Deal Information Model) improved interoperability and cross-domain activities. All datasets in GeoNetwork has a clearly defined license that ensures re-usability of the dataset produced in the Pilots and beyond. In conclusion, the data management plans at the beginning of the project were transformed into practical actions that implemented the plans into all datasets produced and managed by AD4GD.

1 INTRODUCTION

In line with the priorities set forth by the European Commission and the goals of the European Green Deal for a sustainable future, a demand for an open hub for FAIR data with standards-based services is recognised. To achieve these goals, a European Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) has been envisioned to promote these key priorities of the protection of the environment, sustainability and climate-neutrality in the EU, while bolstering the efforts to make data more findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

In line with the above, the establishment of and alignment with an adequate DMP (DMP) is warranted to support the efforts of good data management and a GDDS for the environmental protection and sustainability goals of Europe. In this regard, the previous iterations of the AD4GD DMP included not only the guiding principles behind data management within the project, but also thorough information on:

- the handling of research data;
- how it was collected, processed and stored;
- what standards were applied;
- how data was shared and disseminated.

This included, the protection of personal data, privacy, the ethical use of data, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and any legal provisions that was relevant.

Leveraging and building on previously disseminated Data Management Questionnaires (Annex I), used to collect information from partners individually, the present DMP focuses primarily on the developments at a pilot level, where data collection and generation evolved significantly since the previous iteration.

1.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

In the past decade, environmental and sustainability concerns have become a bigger priority for legislators and decision-makers all over the globe, including Europe. In the European territory, in particular, the European Commission had established a set of priorities, including the European Green Deal¹, which focuses precisely on the achievement of a number of goals related to the protection of the environment and increased sustainability, ultimately aiming at climate-neutrality in the EU by 2050². As such, a major part of the European Green Deal was the establishment of a GDDS to assist the EU in harnessing the power of data towards a sustainable future.

In line with the above, the main objective of the AD4GD was to co-create and shape the European GDDS as an open hub for FAIR data and standards-based services that support the key priorities of biodiversity, climate change, circular economy, deforestation, and pollution.

In order to achieve this, the project focused heavily on interoperability as a solution to the semantic and technology gaps, thus enabling multi-disciplinary and multi-scale access to data, processing services, and

¹ European Commission, 'The European Commission's priorities; 6 Commission priorities for 2019-24' (16 July 2019), available at <https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024_en> [accessed 06 June 2025].

² European Commission, 'A European Green Deal; Striving to be the first climate-neutral continent' (11 December 2019), available at <https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en> [accessed 06 June 2025].

processing platforms. In order to expand more on this main goal, the project's overall objectives were defined as follows:

1. To **co-design a GDDS** consisting of **interoperable** building blocks for heterogeneous data integration, artificial intelligence, Web APIs etc., using **semantic mapping** to allow for multiple existing data models and API standards to be fully integrated.
2. To ensure the **FAIR integration of CitSci** with other in-situ Earth observation data and INSPIRE data in the European GDDS.
3. To enable heterogeneous IoT communication protocols and data format integration into a **common semantic model** for the climate-related, geospatial, and environmental European GDDS.
4. To **overcome data fragmentation** by combining Earth Observation data from satellites with other sources of data into a common climate-related, geospatial, and environmental dataspace to support the European GDDS.
5. To **enhance certainty, quality, and exploitability of heterogeneous data** by leveraging on data analytics, machine learning, and Artificial Intelligence.
6. To demonstrate through multi-scale, multi-criteria, and multi-actor pilots the **applicability and added value of data fusion for improved accessibility decision-making** in the European GDDS domains climate change, zero pollution, and biodiversity.
7. To **research and demonstrate the potential of the AD4GD dataspace** concept from the core to the edge to increase the scalability, performance, and convergence of the use of high-performance computing, cloud, data, and artificial intelligence resources for Earth system modelling.
8. To **upscale and sustain the AD4GD concept and a collaborative community** to support a highly scalable, comprehensive, and FAIR GDDS for citizens, researchers, policy- and decision-makers.

1.2 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

The present document constitutes the final DMP for the AD4GD project. As such, it illustrates the various categories of data that were collected, processed or generated in the course of the project, whether falling under the category of personal data or non-personal data. In this context, the document outlines the work that performed throughout the project's lifecycle with regards to data management aspects, providing the final updates compared to its previous iterations. the standards and principles that were upheld during the project's lifecycle.

In particular, it will focus on the following aspects:

1. A summary of the updates regarding the data that was generated, collected or processed in the course of AD4GD;
2. Outlook on how the project aligned its activities with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (**FAIR**) and Open Science principles;
3. A summary of the **personal data protection and privacy principles, legislation, and guidelines** carefully taken into account by the consortium of partners, in line with the previous DMPs;
4. Overview of the **ethical and legal provisions that were of relevance** to the project's goals and action plan, as well as the project's activities to enhance compliance;
5. The approach that was taken to ensure respect of **IPR**.

1.3 METHODOLOGY

The final DMP (this document) documents how data were generated, processed, and shared throughout the AD4GD project. It reports on the legal and ethical safeguards applied to both personal and non-personal

data, with particular attention to compliance with the GDPR and other relevant EU legislation, as well as the project's activities to enhance compliance. In addition, the project's and partners' final approach towards FAIR data is explained. Finally, this final DMP describes the consortium final strategy regarding the management of IPR.

In order to do the above, this final DMP leverages on the work performed during its previous iterations, collecting and documenting each partner's individual data management activities (previous deliverables; D8,1 and D8,2), and shifts to a more holistic approach, now focusing on the pilot's data-related developments, so as to provide a more comprehensive picture of the project's overall approach towards data, in line with the exploitation plan described in *D7.4 – GDDS Exploitation Perspectives* and to avoid repetition where information was the same.

2 RELEVANT STANDARDS AND PRINCIPLES FOR THE DATA PROCESSING IN AD4GD

2.1 OVERVIEW

As highlighted above, data lies at the very center of the AD4GD project, having shaped the project's activities throughout its lifecycle. With the aim of supporting the GDDS, AD4GD made a **significant contribution to the single market for data**, making available high-quality, interoperable and accessible datasets, as applicable, further promoting the European Strategy for Data. As such, the project was not limited to only collecting and processing data, but it also generated several datasets, ensuring compliance with quality standards, data protection and privacy obligations, as well as any ethical and legal requirements, such as the FAIR data principles and the Artificial Intelligence Act.

Taking the above into account, AD4GD aligned its data provision process with the 2021 UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Science, ensuring that the data was:

- a. **Available in a timely manner,**
- b. **Through a user-friendly format,**
- c. **Human and machine-readable,**
- d. **Actionable,**
- e. **In accordance with the principles of good data governance, stewardship, the FAIR data principles,**
- f. **Supported by regular curation and maintenance.**

Data Management Questionnaires were distributed to partners at the previous stages of the project, which identified the datasets that had already been created, collected and/or processed over the life cycle of the project and their details.

The questionnaire was designed to empower the partners with the ability to review, develop, and report on their data generation and data processing activities, data management strategies and IPR exploitation efforts. It was formed in a way to evolve with the changing nature of the project and reflects the unique characteristics of the partners' datasets.

In this deliverable, the questionnaire was further enhanced and shared with pilot sites' and key asset owners to ensure, on one side, a coordinated reporting and, on the other, a data-related activities duly updated in an efficient manner and in line with the exploitation strategy for harmonisation purposes.

2.1.1 RELEVANCE OF POTENTIAL DATA PROCESSING ACTIVITIES FOR THE PROJECT

AD4GD adopted a dual strategy regarding data management so as to design and implementing its activities in a manner that respects the unique characteristics and needs of both personal and non-personal data, as summarised in the table below:

Table 1: Overall data approach within AD4GD.

Type of Data	Description
Personal Data	The project prioritized the protection of personal data through solutions and policies that aligned with the "privacy by design and by default" principle. Compliance with the GDPR and other EU regulations were upheld with the help of guidance and recommendations provided in the previous iterations of the DMP. An analysis of the Data Management Questionnaires sent out to the consortium of partners was conducted to provide more detailed and specific guidelines on the relevant legal obligations based on the partner's roles and actions within the project.
Non-personal data	The project facilitated the sharing of non-personal data in a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) manner, ensuring that datasets remained interoperable and available to the scientific community and industry. Making the data accessible was at the center of the project's activities, so that they can be reused to support a GDDS in advancing the objectives of the EU Strategy's goals for environmental protection and to prevent climate change.

In line with the above, and with the achievement of the project primary objectives regarding **semantic interoperability**, AD4GD developed datasets for testing and validating data integration. This approach demonstrates the value of data fusion and highlights its potential in improving decision-making processes within the GDDS through enhanced accessibility.

By enabling the seamless integration of data from diverse sources in an **interoperable, scalable, and reliable manner**, datasets made available by AD4GD could be included in to knowledge centers, the GEOSS portal, and other relevant scientific services.

2.1.2 CATEGORIES OF DATA, DATA SOURCES AND DATA SECURITY

Within the AD4GD project, various datasets were processed and generated, encompassing different categories of data. These datasets served specific purpose in the context of meeting the project's objectives. The data in question can be summarised as follows:

Table 2: Data collection and generation overview within AD4GD.

Categories of Data	Data Type	Data Collection/ Generation	Data Description
Personal Data	Citizens' data, as active sensors in a network of observations.	Data Collection	Citizen's data may be incidentally collected from IoT devices in the process of collecting and processing geo-located data. Where such data was collected, it was anonymized to the greater extent possible, while the project leveraged on synergies thanks to the Big Data Value Partnership that provided invaluable insights on privacy-preserving technologies and cybersecurity measures that were implemented.

Non-personal data	IoT data, statistical data and community observations.	Data Generation	Such data were used to develop the algorithmic models to improve existing Earth observation models.
	Governmental, commercial and volunteered data.	Data Collection and Generation.	Were combined using adaptors and semantic mappings, which should themselves be accessible as FAIR services, aiming at improving the quality and reliability of the data.
	Data coming from existing networks of in-situ observatories.	Data Collection and Generation.	Such data were collected from existing network, such as the ENVRI plus network, the European Citizen Science association and the INSPIRE community. They were then used to design and implement an approach based on dialogue and co-creation so as to define the EV framework.
	In-situ observations, socioeconomic data and CitSci data.	Data Collection and Generation.	Such data was collected and integrated in order to design and cross-validate alternative models for generating environmental metrics.
	Satellite and Earth observations.	Data Collection and Generation.	These types of data were collected and used to determine, following a multi-actor approach with the involvement of relevant stakeholders and users, a range of datasets that can support a thorough testing of the proposed semantic model and which can be effectively accessed for the project's case studies.

Deliverable *D6.2 – Pilot Technical Implementation Planning, Implementation and Assessment* also presents in detail the proposed AD4GD Dataspace and its relation to the pilots, in alignment with FAIRness, data sovereignty and trust, further detailing the data collection, generation and its journey.

2.1.3 PILOT DATA FLOWS

In addition to the overview provided above, this sub-section presents simplified versions of the data flows, as further analysed in *D6.2 – Pilot Implementation Planning, Implementation and Assessment*. These data flows help further visualise the data collection, processing and generation activities within the pilot sites in a manner that is simple and comprehensive.

2.1.3.1 PILOT 1

Pilot 1³ focuses on the development of tools and indices to monitor and improve the management of small urban lakes, which play vital ecological and recreational roles but are often neglected in traditional water monitoring frameworks, using the city of Berlin as an example. As such, the pilot combined data from satellite observations, IoT sensors, and Citizen Science inputs with AI-driven analytics to create a Water Quality Index (WQI) and Water Availability Index (WAI).

The figure below presents precisely those data flows within Pilot 1 that enabled it to provide a scalable solution that can enhance water management in Berlin and be transferred to similar urban environments.

Figure 1: Simplified data flow diagram for pilot 1 showing input data sources, scenario modelling, computed indices and a UI.

2.1.3.2 PILOT 2

Pilot 2⁴ focuses on advancing biodiversity conservation by evaluating functional landscape connectivity (FLC) in Catalonia, Spain, in alignment with global and European biodiversity strategies, including the European Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. Pilot 2 integrated satellite, administrative, and Citizen Science data with analysis to deliver actionable insights into ecological corridors and species

³ <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-1>

⁴ <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2>

movement to assess and enhance landscape connectivity, supporting informed decision-making among stakeholders, from policymakers to local biodiversity initiatives.

The figure below presents the data flows within Pilot 2 helping it provide scalable, FAIR data tools to achieve its objectives.

Figure 2: Simplified data flow diagram for pilot 2 showing the input data used at different stages of the pipeline.

2.1.3.3 PILOT 3

Pilot 3 focusses on evaluating the potential usefulness of IoT derived air quality data for future forecasting applications. Pilot 3 derived from the Sensor Community (formerly Luftdaten) project, and standardised, analysed for outliers and constrained or scaled using the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) air quality forecast analysis data.

The figure below demonstrates the data flows required to achieve the above.

Figure 3: Simplified data flow diagram for pilot 3.

2.2 DATA QUALITY

Given the nature of the data, as described in the previous section, as well as the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods and tools, to ensure the quality of the data was a priority for the project. In order to achieve this, the project focused on trustworthiness methodology applied in the 3 pilots and described in D4.3.

As an example, the project developed and implemented an **IoT Measurements Correction Model**, applying a statistical adjustment to IoT PM observations by rescaling them based on co-located reference measurements from EEA stations. The mentioned model, including its latest updates, incorporates spatial data aggregation and improved learning techniques to ensure that the reference data can be meaningfully compared to the corresponding IoT measurements. Once trained, the model was applied to correct IoT time series. For sensors that belong to a known cluster, the corresponding model prediction is used directly. For sensors outside of any defined cluster, corrected values are estimated using an inverse distance weighted ensemble of predictions from all available clusters. This approach ensured spatial continuity and enabled reliable correction even in regions with sparse or missing reference data.

2.2.1 PILOT 1

Given the focus of pilot 1 on water quality, satellite data was the primary source of information. That being said, such data was not always available or of sufficient quality, so alternatives needed to be discovered. During the project, citizen science proved to be very promising for gathering basic information about small lakes. Wherever the resolution of satellite data is insufficient or a large part of the water body is covered by tree crowns and sensors are too expensive and too time-consuming to maintain, citizen science data was used as the main way to collect data continuously.

As such, a questionnaire was created specifically for small urban lakes to be used in the CrowdWater⁵ app. The questions can be answered without in-depth knowledge of water bodies and were translated into 18 languages. As with many citizen science projects, the results are often subjective. A question about the colour of the water may be answered with green or brown, depending on the person, and the question of whether one would swim in the water involves a great deal of subjective assessment. At KWB, a targeted evaluation of the answers was developed to obtain indicators on the nutrient situation, the lake biotope, usage, and water requirements. To calculate the indicator for the nutrient situation, selected answer options are assigned positive (low nutrients) or negative (high nutrients) points.

2.2.2 PILOT 2

The focus of Pilot 2, as described above, lies in biodiversity aspects, for which multiple indices may be used, including differences between the ground-truth and modelled habitat connectivity, Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Structural Similarity Index (SSIM).

Given the variations of said indices, the project relied on a combination of indices per output image describing habitat connectivity, in order to validate the results and not rely on a single metric that may have proven to be unrealistic or erroneous.

2.2.3 PILOT 3

In order to achieve the objectives of Pilot 3 related to air quality, a machine learning model with meteorological variables (e.g. from the ERA5) was trained for the rescaling of the data.

In order to minimise error in this process and ensure high quality and accuracy of data, the scaled data was then compared with in-situ reference measurements from official air quality monitoring stations of various European environmental authorities provided by the European Environment Agency (EEA)

⁵ <https://crowdwater.ch/en/what-is-crowdwater/>

3 FAIR DATA

FAIR data is defined as the data that was findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. As such, alignment with the FAIR principles is essential for the AD4GD's goals and the aspirations of the European GDDS. In this way, researchers and institutions can better collaborate, innovate and advance scientific progress, and at the same time, increase transparency, knowledge-sharing and reproducibility of their work. Within this section, the project's activities towards ensuring that its data and results are complying with FAIR and Open Science principles will be described in a three-fold manner:

- A. Summarising the **overall strategy** that was followed within the project and envisioned for after its conclusion;
- B. Analysing in a dedicated section the **FAIR aspects of the pilots' datasets**;
- C. Analysing in a dedicated section the **FAIR aspects of the rest of AD4GD key assets**, in line with the exploitation approach described in *D7.4 – GDDS Exploitation Perspectives*.

3.1 OVERALL FAIR STRATEGY WITHIN AD4GD

This section provides more details on the aspects associated with each of the FAIR aspects, as well as the project's overall approach towards aligning with them.

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE

Findability focuses on ensuring that both data and metadata generated are made available in a manner that ensures they can be located by interested parties.

In order to make data and metadata findable, it is essential that it meets the following conditions:

- i. It is assigned a **globally unique and persistent identifier**;
- ii. It is described with **rich standardised metadata**;
- iii. It is registered or indexed in a **searchable resource**.

As such, AD4GD recognised since the start the need for **standard agreements on metadata aspects for discovery, APIs and resource models** that will interact with the environmental service information system.

STANDARDISED DATA AND METADATA

The projects incorporated from early on **recognized vocabularies and standardised metadata**, and established a **Metadata Working Group** in charge of adequately formulating the metadata relevant for each dataset and person in CREAM (coordinator) to supervise the process. The metadata was elaborated following existing standards (e.g. DCAT, GeoDCAT⁶, ISO 19115⁷) so that the best-fitted data sources can be discovered and matched to the most appropriate stages of a scientific workflow.

As such, a solution providing access to internal users via a cloud based MinIO repository for data storage (and for connector deployment for data sharing) was chosen, along with the implementation of a GeoNetwork metadata catalogue (based on ISO 19115 metadata standards) that exports to Data Catalogue

⁶ <https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/releases/>

⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/26020.html>

Vocabulary (DCAT)⁸ metadata that is the standard used by Eclipse Dataspace Connectors (EDC) in compliance with IDSA Dataspace Protocol⁹.

Metadata on MinIO

The files stored in MinIO incorporate a minimum set of metadata information according to the Amazon S3 cloud specification. The metadata can be added to the files stored in MinIO and this metadata is made available when the file is downloaded by including HTTP headers with names that begin with the X-Amz-Meta- prefix.

The number of attributes to be included is unlimited as long as it is of a flat structure. This was considered a proof of concept, and more attributes could be added for convenience in the future. The following Figure includes an example of the metadata exposed in the MinIO.

The screenshot shows the MinIO Object Store interface. The main content area displays a table of objects under the path 'pilot1.predictions'. The selected object is '5800310_predictions_high_precipitations_2025-06-05.jsonld'. The 'Metadata' section is highlighted with a red box and contains the following information:

Field	Value
Content-Type	application/json
X-Amz-Meta-Data	Water Level Predictions
X-Amz-Meta-Lake_Id	5800310
X-Amz-Meta-Project	AD4GD
X-Amz-Meta-Starting-Date	2025-06-05

Figure 4: Metadata exposed in MinIO console.

However, since this is not a standard approach to describe metadata, every time a new AD4GD dataset is made available in MinIO, it is also documented in GeoNetwork metadata catalogue following the ISO19115 standard and then exposed as an asset in the EDC federated catalogue as DCAT¹⁰.

AD4GD GEONETWORK METADATA CATALOGUE FOR DISCOVERY AND ACCESS

The AD4GD project deployed a GeoNetwork metadata catalogue to register the metadata of all datasets in the project pilots. GeoNetwork is an open-source geospatial catalogue application used for managing, discovering, and sharing geospatial metadata. It facilitates the creation of metadata catalogues that describe geospatial resources, such as datasets, services, and other geographical information. The primary goal of GeoNetwork is to improve discoverability of geospatial information by providing a standardised and interoperable platform. The URL of the GeoNetwork is: <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd>.

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

⁹ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/offers/dataspace-protocol/>

¹⁰ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/dataspace-protocol>

GeoNetwork offers native support for the ISO19115/ISO19139 geospatial metadata and can export metadata into DCAT format. The AD4GD project specifically adopts the ISO19115:2003 version of the standard, which is widely used worldwide, such as by the European Spatial Data Infrastructure (INSPIRE). At the same time, the GDDS is expected to follow the IDSA recommendations and adopt the DCAT standard. GeoNetwork exposes metadata through the Open Geospatial Catalogue Service for the Web (OGC-CSW)¹¹ and supports retrieving metadata through HTTP requests in both ISO19115/19139 and DCAT standard formats, making it well aligned to the needs of AD4GD and the overall GDDS.

Despite the rules to create quality metadata offered by ISO specifications, there may be several acceptable ways to describe the same property. Thus, to promote consistency and facilitate the metadata creation process, specific templates were prepared for each type of data source to describe the dataset, as well as a set of best practices to follow were produced and documented in AD4GD GitHub at <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-GeoNetwork>, as demonstrated in the figure below.

Figure 5: AD4GD metadata templates.

GeoNetwork supports different user roles (e.g., reviewer, editor, and administrator). Within AD4GD, CREAM partner was designated as the catalogue administrator and the responsible to ensure that the established best practices are followed and that all metadata records are complete and documented in a consistent way.

In addition to the above, the following table presents the ISO 19115 core metadata elements in relation with those used to document AD4GD pilot datasets as included in D4.3.

Table 3: ISO 19115 core metadata elements used to document the AD4GD pilot datasets

ISO19115 element	Domain	Description	Obligation	AD4GD metadata

¹¹ <https://docs.ogc.org/is/12-168r6/12-168r6.html>

ISO19115 element	Domain	Description	Obligation	AD4GD metadata
Dataset title	MD_DataIdentification.citation > CI_Citation.title	Title of the dataset	Mandatory	Yes
Dataset reference date	MD_DataIdentification.citation > CI_Citation.date	Date of the metadata record creation, revision, etc	Mandatory	Yes
Dataset responsible party	MD_DataIdentification.pointOfContact > CI_ResponsibleParty	Party who authored/owns/supplies/is responsible/has processed/has published the resource	Mandatory	Yes
Geographic location of the dataset	MD_DataIdentification.extent > EX_Extent > EX_GeographicExtent = EX_GeographicBoundingBox or EX_GeographicDescription	Spatial extent information, including the geographic coverage of the dataset defined by a bounding box (westLon, eastLon, southLat, northLat)	Conditional	Yes
Dataset language	MD_DataIdentification.language	Language used for documenting the metadata	Mandatory	Yes
Dataset character set	MD_DataIdentification.characterSet	Character set in which the dataset is encoded	Conditional	Yes
Dataset topic category	MD_DataIdentification.topicCategory	ISO Topic Categories	Mandatory	Yes
Keywords	MD_DataIdentification.Keyword	keywords that identifies a particular subject, object, or topic represented by the dataset according to the GEMET-INSPIRE, OGC RAINBOW, MiraMon Thesaurus, ELTER Vocabularies and Climate and Forecast Standard Names (NVS). Custom keywords are also used to filter metadata records by AD4GD pilot	Optional	Yes
Spatial resolution of the dataset	MD_DataIdentification.spatialResolution > MD_Resolution.equivalentScale or MD_Resolution.distance	Level of detail expressed as a scale factor or a ground sample distance (pixels per meter or geographic scale)	Optional	If applicable
Abstract describing the dataset	MD_DataIdentification.abstract	Short description of the dataset, including possible links to examples of application	Mandatory	Yes

ISO19115 element	Domain	Description	Obligation	AD4GD metadata
Distribution format	MD_Distribution > MD_Format.name and MD_Format.version	Format of the data described	Optional	Yes
Additional extent information for the dataset	MD_DataIdentification.extent > EX_Extent > EX_TemporalExtent or EX_VerticalExtent	Temporal validity or coverage of the dataset	Optional	Yes
Spatial representation type	MD_DataIdentification.spatialRepresentationType	Digital method used to spatially represent geographic information, depending on whether it is vector or grid data	Optional	Yes
Reference system	MD_ReferenceSystem	Spatial reference system, defined by geographic coordinates according the EPSG codes	Optional	Yes
Lineage	DQ_DataQuality.lineage > LI_Lineage	Information about the events or source data used in constructing the described data	Optional	If possible
On-line resource	MD_Distribution > MD_DigitalTransferOption.onLine > CI_OnlineResource	URL or location path where is possible to find the dataset (e.g., MinIO, FROST or ODC)	Optional	If possible
Metadata file identifier	MD_Metadata.fileIdentifier	Identifier of the metadata record	Optional	Yes
Metadata standard name	MD_Metadata.metadataStandardName	Name of the standard used to document the metadata	Optional	Yes
Metadata standard version	MD_Metadata.metadataStandardVersion	Version of the metadata standard	Optional	Yes
Metadata language	MD_Metadata.language	Language or languages in which the metadata is provided	Conditional	Yes
Metadata character set	MD_Metadata.characterSet	Character set used to encode the metadata	Conditional	Yes
Metadata	MD_Metadata.contact >	Point of contact for the content of the	Mandatory	Yes

ISO19115 element	Domain	Description	Obligation	AD4GD metadata
point of contact	CI_ResponsibleParty	metadata		
Metadata date stamp	MD_Metadata.dateStamp	Date in which the metadata was created	Mandatory	Yes

As a summary, the following Figure illustrates the flow of data and metadata, as was reported in *D4.3 – Connecting the GDDS*. The most important thing in the diagram is that in time series production, GeoNetwork stores a single metadata record describing the product and MinIO provides the dates of each file in the time series.

Figure 6: AD4GD data and metadata flow.

3.1.2 MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

Once data is found, there needs to be the possibility to access it, whether without additional steps or after authentication and/or authorisation was concluded. In order for data to be considered accessible, it needs to meet the following criteria:

- i. It is **retrievable by its identifier using a standardized communication protocol**;
- ii. The protocol used is **open, free, and universally implementable**;
- iii. The protocol used allows for an **authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary**;
- iv. It permits for **metadata to be accessible**, even when the data no longer is.

As already explained, the project leveraged on **existing standardized metadata and communications protocols**.

AD4GD adopted 3 approaches to data accessibility:

- For small datasets that can be downloaded as files, the GeoNetwork "attach" mechanism is used in order to allow for uploading data to GeoNetwork and link it as attachments to the metadata.
- For bigger datasets, they are made accessible as web services for visualization and downloading. The Catalan Data Cube is one possible web service available. The service access point already been linked to the GeoNetwork metadata record.
- For time series processed data GeoNetwork contains only one record describing the time series but it links to the files in MinIO

In summary, GeoNetwork metadata records always report distribution options on how to obtain the data as links independently of its origins. In line with the above, data was also uploaded on a MinIO instance for internal processing purposes and made available to the rest of the project participants.

All information on the Pilots that can be access, was made available on the project's website¹². These results are presented in a user-friendly format, allowing interested stakeholders to access and download. Further dissemination materials (video, article, blogpost) were made available on Zenodo¹³ and Cordis¹⁴.

What is more, the detailed cookbook on how to replicate **Pilot 1 Water quality** is available in GitHub¹⁵ under an open- source license allowing developers and the scientific community to replicate or reuse components of the pilot and recreate the whole.

Similarly, additional dissemination materials, including tutorials, [GitHub](#)¹⁶ repositories, and blog content related to **Pilot 3** are hosted via ECMWF platforms and partner channels and archived (e.g. on Zenodo). The full data processing workflow, including code samples and documentation, was made openly available on GitHub under an open-source license. This ensures that developers, researchers, and public interest groups can reuse or adapt the workflow to suit other geographies, datasets, or use cases.

The following tables were originally presented in *D7.4 – GDDS Exploitation Perspectives* and include the location from where the pilots primary results can be accessed.

Table 4: Specific tools and dissemination materials for Pilot 1.

Title	Function	Access type	Access link
GitHub	Pilot 1 Water quality - how to replicate guides, codes	Public, open-source	https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-1-water-quality
SplashBoard	A visual, interactive interface for comparing water status across	Public after	https://apps.apple.com/gb/app/splashboard/id15314690

¹² <https://ad4gd.eu/deliverables/>

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/records/10839023>

¹⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101061001/reporting>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-1-water-quality>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-3-air-quality>

GUI	multiple lakes.	registration	09
Dissemination material	Splashboard description	Public after registration	https://ad4gd.fit.fraunhofer.de/splashboard
Dissemination material	Pilot 1 Water quality description	Public after registration	https://ad4gd.eu/water-pollution/
CrowdWater App	Citizen science input for hydrological observations.	Public after registration	https://crowdwater.ch/en/start/
Dissemination video	This video presents the Splashboard graphical interface developed as part of the All Data for Green Deal (AD4GD) project.	Public	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9Jbj8Uv-0bg&list=PL5v0XQ3VTFly2cHEcXbL2D69s4MaXPUEj&index=4
Dissemination video	Malte Zamzow (KWB, AD4GD) presented the results of the water pilot in AD4GD.	Public	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tED0gS6n7Vk&list=PL5v0XQ3VTFly2cHEcXbL2D69s4MaXPUEj&index=19

Table 5: Specific tools and dissemination materials for Pilot 2.

Name of Tool	Function	Access Type	Access Link
BioConnect Tool	visual, interactive tool	Public, Open source	https://github.com/AD4GD/Pilots-Graphical-User-Interfaces
Data4Land	enriching land use/land cover (LULC) datasets	Public, Open source	https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2-preprocessing
Open Data Cube (ODC)	Earth observation data processing	Public, Open source	https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-OAPI_CoveragesForODC

Dissemination material	Dissemination video on Bioconnect Graphical User Interface - Kristian Berwanger (Fraunhofer FIT, AD4GD)	Public	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YbU-YdHmCyU&list=PL5v0XQ3VTFly2cHEcXbL2D69s4MaXPUEj&index=10
Dissemination material	Dissemination video on Data4Land: How to Enrich Land Use/Land Cover Datasets? - Vitalii Kriukov (Aston University, AD4GD)	Public	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=agg0Sdb2ePA&list=PL5v0XQ3VTFly2cHEcXbL2D69s4MaXPUEj&index=18

Table 6: Specific tools and dissemination materials for Pilot 3.

Name of Tool	Function	Access Type	Access Link
ECMWF Air Quality Dataset	Harmonised air quality data from IoT and validated sources	Public	xds.ecmwf.int
GitHub Repository	Codebase for data processing, documentation, and tutorials	Public, open-source	https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-3-air-quality
Tutorial Materials	Jupyter-based walkthroughs for dataset exploration and comparison	Public	https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-3-air-quality/tree/main/demos

3.1.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Interoperability was highlighted as the main component of the project's objectives. In order to align with interoperability requirements, the below described general conditions must be met:

- i. Both data and metadata need to use a **formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language** for knowledge representation;
- ii. Both data and metadata need to use **vocabularies that are compliant with FAIR principles**;
- iii. Both data and metadata need to include **qualified references to other data and metadata**.

In that sense, AD4GD links interoperability and reusability of FAIR data to clearly communicating its provenance and documenting the transformations undergone, as well as recording more traditional summaries of data quality to assess whether they are fit for new users.

The project had a full WP devoted to semantic interoperability on the GDDS (WP1) creating and using the Green Deal Information Model (GDIM). Tools, such as the *OGC rainbow* (formerly known as *OGC definition server*), the AD4GD information model, the meaning catalogue, the meaning service and TAPIS gives support on semantic annotation. AD4GD developed and tested **semantic interoperability approaches** suitable for incorporating IoT and other data streams currently not being harvested and available in contemporary data platforms.

3.1.4 RE-USE OF DATA

Reusability ensures that data can be reused by other parties, including researchers, to the benefit of society as a whole. In order for data to be reusable, they must meet the following minimum set of criteria¹⁷:

- i. Both data and metadata need to be **richly described** with a plurality of accurate and relevant
- ii. Attributes;
- iii. Both data and metadata need to be **released with a clear and accessible data usage license**;
- iv. Both data and metadata need to be **associated with detailed provenance**;
- v. Both data and metadata need to meet **domain-relevant community standards**

The project's general approach was based on **co-creation and co-design of the Dataspace with the community of data providers and end-users**, establishing a common semantic interoperability framework that enhances the usability of data and their corresponding information so as to support of the European Green Deal strategies.

Existing standards and ontologies will be exploited, wherever possible, including PROV, UncertML and QualityML and PPSR_CORE. Standards and vocabularies for documenting provenance, QA and QC of remote sensing data, as well as for IoT sensors and networks (e.g. Sensor Things API, SensorML, the Semantic Sensor Network Ontology) were also used, as described above.

In addition to the above, a set of policy and standard contributions were made in order to further enhance the reusability of the AD4GD results. The table below provides an overview of those contributions, their location and access type, as was reported in *D7.4 – GDDS Exploitation Perspectives*.

Table 7: Specific tools and dissemination materials for standards.

Title	Description	Access type	Access link
Brief on the recommendations	The four sibling projects collaborated to produce a concise Policy Brief focused on five pillars critical to the success of the GDDS: data harmonization, semantic interoperability, metadata management, data exchange, and governance.	Public	https://zenodo.org/records/15649164

¹⁷ Ibid no 4.

Title	Description	Access type	Access link
Standards	OGC API - Tiles - Part 1: Core	Public	https://docs.ogc.org/is/20-057/20-057.html
Standards	OGC Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF Standard	Public	https://docs.ogc.org/is/21-026/21-026.html
Standards	OGC API - Maps - Part 1: Core	Public	https://docs.ogc.org/is/20-058/20-058.html
Standards	FIWARE smart data models extension	Public	https://www.fiware.org/smart-data-models/
Dissemination video	Policy Brief Launch - Unlocking the Full Potential of the GDDS - GDDS	Public	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H_IXN3FPyiY&list=PL5v0XQ3VTFly2cHEcXbL2D69s4MaXPUEj&index=26

3.2 ALIGNMENT OF PILOT DATASETS WITH FAIR PRINCIPLES

This section will delve deeper into the pilots' dedicated datasets, providing an in-depth presentation of the related information.

3.2.1 PILOT 1

This section provides the full description of the datasets included in the GeoNetwork regarding Pilot 1.

Table 8: Pilot 1 Datasets.

Grunewaldsee- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Grunewaldsee lake: Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/alf354d9-457b-4640-ab2c-8c6bc1ded30e/attachments/Grunewaldsee.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Groß Glienicker See- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Grossglienickersee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV

Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/ee6a3c20-ae6a-422e-88d9-6bed9fcd77b/attachments/Grossglienickersee.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Fennpfuhl- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Fennpfuhl lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/99018830-b07f-4115-92f9-1afbdefa9b20/attachments/Fennpfuhl.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Dianasee - water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Dianasee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature

Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/f7bf1553-4c71-484b-ba3c-d4b28477fa4a/attachments/Dianasee.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Biesdorfer Baggersee- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Biesdorfer Baggersee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/6231e4ef-368b-444b-86d1-77adf24a9cbd/attachments/biesdorferbaggersee.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Fennsee- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Fennsee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No

Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/0c9bd113-9fd2-4079-b81c-002792786bab/attachments/Fennsee.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Malchowersee- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Malchowersee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/9a66e2ea-9839-4450-9899-ae7363c230f6/attachments/Malchowersee.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Berlin Lake Mueggelsee Water Quality Dataset (AD4GD copy hosted on MinIO)

Dataset(s) description	Lake Mueggelsee Water Quality Dataset downloaded from https://fred.igb-berlin.de/data/package/165 . The dataset is provided by the Müggelsee station 165. Sampling interval is 30 secs. Note on interval before 2011: the interval was 1 hour. Historic data is available for the time period 14/04/2005 - 05/12/2022. The Müggelsee, also known as the Großer Müggelsee, is a natural lake in the eastern edge of Berlin, the capital city of Germany. It is the largest of the Berlin lakes by area, with an area of 7.4 square kilometres (2.9 sq mi), a length of 4.3 kilometres (2.7 mi).
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Berlin Lake Water Quality
Data format	CSV
Data Storage	AD4GD copy hosted on MinIO
Dataset Links	https://minio.dashboard-siba.store/browser/pilot.1/aWdiX211Z18xNjUv
Data Ownership	EVIDEN test@eviden.com
Country of Origin	Germany
Restrictions on the use	Requires MinIO credentials for data access. This dataset is not Open Access and was provided to EVIDEN on request.
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Obersee- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Obersee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/632c0937-77f3-4696-a417-d745f4b48532/attachments/Obersee.csv?approved=true

Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

dreipfuhl- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Dreipfuhl lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/2db6bc81-0550-4adf-9988-edc4feb35026/attachments/Dreipfuhl.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Continuous E.coli measurements in surface water

Dataset(s) description	Online measurements of E.coli with device: Adasa AquaBio. Device installed in river Spree in the Berlin city center during september and october 2023.
Personal Data	No
Purpose	E.coli, River, Indicator organisms, Surface Water, Water quality, Combined sewer overflow, Urban water cycle, Bathing waters
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/srv/api/records/e609d591-daf5-49c0-b91d-05d46957072c/attachments/aquabio.json

Data Ownership	KWB wolfgang.seis@kompetenz-wasser.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Restrictions on the use	Restricted
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Halensee- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Halensee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/04e52744-7978-42d7-a01b-47b2588ace5c/attachments/Halensee.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Orankesee- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Orankesee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature

Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/651b49f1-195f-4efb-b2c2-f2ec2f89e370/attachments/Orankesee.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Waldsee Zehlendorf- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Waldseezehendorf lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/2b64d421-ca5d-4fa0-bd29-89fd40075444/attachments/Waldseezehendorf.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Plötzensee- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Plotzensee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No

Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/b3656bd9-c0df-4e8b-b60a-ae57b9494f50/attachments/Plotzensee.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Hundekehlesee lake (Station ID: 5800308) - Water temperature and water level data

Dataset(s) description	Hundekehlesee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/srv/api/records/63ae32b2-2f5c-418a-bd72-439d17b3131c/attachments/Hundekehlesee.csv
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Flughafensee- water level and water temperature

Dataset(s) description	Flughafensee lake: The Berlin water portal provides information on current and historical measured values from the Berlin state monitoring networks for surface water (rivers and lakes), soil water and groundwater (aquifers). Useful links: Main landing page: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php Measured values: Water Temperature (°C) Water level (cm)
Personal Data	No

Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/b297c4d0-ad7c-4211-abe2-9eb3e4ba98dc/attachments/Flughafensee.csv?approved=true
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.
Dataset(s) name	Schäfersee lake (Station ID: 5800106) - Water temperature and water level data
Dataset(s) description	This data consists on water temperature and water level measurements for Schäfersee Lake at hourly basis (15 minute intervals) and on a daily basis, filtered for selected time periods, in both raw (CSV) and harmonized (JSON-LD) formats. The data originates from an in-situ monitoring station and is considered representative of the entire lake. It is made available through the Berlin Wasserportal (https://wasserportal.berlin.de). It is stored in a MinIO server and a FROST server managed by the AD4GD project. Measuring point information -Station ID: 5800106 - Location (UTM Zone 33N, EPSG:32633): --Easting: 384121 --Northing: 5818969 Measured parameters -Water Temperature (°C) -Water Level (cm) Generic paths - Path to MinIO GUI enviroment: https://minio-ad4gd-console.dashboard-siba.store/browser/ -Path to MinIO API: https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/ -Path to FROST server: https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?\$filter=substringof('Wasserportal Berlin - Water Temperature',name)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level and water temperature
Data format	CSV

Dataset Links

https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/watertemperature/5800106_wassertemperatur_ew_19_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/watertemperature/5800106_wassertemperatur_ew_27_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/waterlevel/5800106_wasserstand_ew_19_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/waterlevel/5800106_wasserstand_ew_27_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/watertemperature/5800106_wassertemperatur_tw_01_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/watertemperature/5800106_wassertemperatur_tw_26_03_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/watertemperature/5800106_wassertemperatur_tw_30_03_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/waterlevel/5800106_wasserstand_tw_01_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/waterlevel/5800106_wasserstand_tw_26_03_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/watertemperature/5800106_wasserstand_tw_30_03_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/watertemperature/5800106_wassertemperatur_tw_01_01_2025.jsonld
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/watertemperature/5800106_wassertemperatur_tw_26_03_2025.jsonld
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/watertemperature/5800106_wassertemperatur_tw_30_03_2025.jsonld
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/waterlevel/5800106_wasserstand_tw_01_01_2025.jsonld
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/waterlevel/5800106_wasserstand_tw_26_03_2025.jsonld
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/waterlevel/5800106_wasserstand_tw_30_03_2025.jsonld
[https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?\\$filter=substringof\('%27Station%20number:%205800106%27,description\)%20and%20substringof\('%27Wasserportal%20Berlin%20-%20Water%20Level%27,name\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?$filter=substringof('%27Station%20number:%205800106%27,description)%20and%20substringof('%27Wasserportal%20Berlin%20-%20Water%20Level%27,name))
[https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?\\$filter=substringof\('%27Station%20number:%205800106%27,description\)%20and%20substringof\('%27Wasserportal%20Berlin%20-%20Water%20Temperature%27,name\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?$filter=substringof('%27Station%20number:%205800106%27,description)%20and%20substringof('%27Wasserportal%20Berlin%20-%20Water%20Temperature%27,name))

Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Krumme Lanke Berlin (Station ID: 5800107) - Water Level data

Dataset(s) description	Station ID: 5800107; Station Name: Am Wolfsschluchtkanal; Surface Water: Krumme Lanke; Further information: https://wasserportal.berlin.de/station.php?anzeige=i&thema=ows&station=5800107
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water level data
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://www.berlin.de/sen/uvk/en/ https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

CrowdWater data - Citizen science observations in the Berlin lakes

Dataset(s) description	Hydrological observations in the Berlin metropolitan area captured by citizens using the CrowdWater App (https://crowdwater.ch). The data is stored in a MinIO server managed by the AD4GD project. Attributes: ID, ROOT_ID, LATITUDE, LONGITUDE, CREATED_AT, MODIFIED_AT, PRESELECT_WATER_TYPE, CATEGORY, IMAGE, LAKE_USAGE, LAKE_ACCESS, LAKE_SHORE_STATE, LITTER_IN_WATER, LAKE_SWIM, LAKE_TRANSPARENCY, LAKE_WATER_COLOUR, LAKE_SMELL, LAKE_SHORE_VEGETATION, LAKE_PLANTS_UNDERWATER, FLOATING_LEAVE_PLANTS, DUCKWEED, LAKE_MUSSELS, LAKE_DEADWOOD, LAKE_ANIMALS, LAKE_WATER_LEVEL, LAKE_DRIES_OUT, PHYSICAL_SCALE_UNIT, PHYSICAL_SCALE_LEVEL, SPOTTED_AT, DESCRIPTION MinIO path: https://minio-ad4gd-console.dashboard-siba.store/browser/pilot.1/crowdwater_data/crowdwater_lakes_berlin.csv
Personal Data	No

Purpose	Water body, Lake, Citizen science, lake usage, lake access, lake shore state, litter in water, lake swim, lake transparency, lake water colour, lake smell, lake shore vegetation, lake plants underwater, floating leave plants, duckweed, lake mussels, lake deadwood, lake animals, lake water level, lake dries out
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/crowdwater_data/crowdwater_lakes_berlin.csv
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Lietensee lake (Station ID: 5800309) - Water temperature and water level data

Dataset(s) description	This data consists on water temperature and water level measurements for Lietensee Lake at hourly basis (15 minute intervals) and on a daily basis, filtered for selected time periods, in both raw (CSV) and harmonized (JSON-LD) formats. The data originates from an in-situ monitoring station and is considered representative of the entire lake. It is made available through the Berlin Wasserportal (https://wasserportal.berlin.de). It is stored in a MinIO server and a FROST server managed by the AD4GD project. Measuring point information -Station ID: 5800309 - Location (UTM Zone 33N, EPSG:32633): --Easting: 384121 --Northing: 5818969 Measured parameters -Water Temperature (°C) -Water Level (cm) Generic paths - Path to MinIO GUI enviroment: https://minio-ad4gd-console.dashboard-siba.store/browser/ -Path to MinIO API: https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/ -Path to FROST server: https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?\$filter=substringof('Wasserportal Berlin - Water Temperature',name)
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Water temperature and water level data
Data format	CSV

Dataset Links

https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/watertemperature/5800309_wassertemperatur_ew_19_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/watertemperature/5800309_wassertemperatur_ew_27_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/waterlevel/5800309_wasserstand_ew_19_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/hourlyData/waterlevel/5800309_wasserstand_ew_27_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/watertemperature/5800309_wassertemperatur_tw_01_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/watertemperature/5800309_wassertemperatur_tw_26_03_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/watertemperature/5800309_wassertemperatur_tw_30_03_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/waterlevel/5800309_wasserstand_tw_01_01_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/waterlevel/5800309_wasserstand_tw_26_03_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/dailyData/watertemperature/5800309_wasserstand_tw_30_03_2025.csv
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/watertemperature/5800309_wassertemperatur_tw_01_01_2025.jsonld
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/watertemperature/5800309_wassertemperatur_tw_26_03_2025.jsonld
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/watertemperature/5800309_wassertemperatur_tw_30_03_2025.jsonld
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/waterlevel/5800309_wasserstand_tw_01_01_2025.jsonld
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/waterlevel/5800309_wasserstand_tw_26_03_2025.jsonld
https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1.harmonized/waterlevel/5800309_wasserstand_tw_30_03_2025.jsonld
[https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?\\$filter=substringof\('%27Station%20number:%205800309%27,description\)%20and%20substringof\('%27Wasserportal%20Berlin%20-%20Water%20Level%27,name\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?$filter=substringof('%27Station%20number:%205800309%27,description)%20and%20substringof('%27Wasserportal%20Berlin%20-%20Water%20Level%27,name))
[https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?\\$filter=substringof\('%27Station%20number:%205800309%27,description\)%20and%20substringof\('%27Wasserportal%20Berlin%20-%20Water%20Temperature%27,name\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/Things?$filter=substringof('%27Station%20number:%205800309%27,description)%20and%20substringof('%27Wasserportal%20Berlin%20-%20Water%20Temperature%27,name))

Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Geometries of Berlin lakes

Dataset(s) description	Geometries of Berlin lakes
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Geometries, Inland water, Lake locations, Surface water, Water, Water bodies
Data format	CSV
Data Storage	https://minio-ad4gd-api.dashboard-siba.store/pilot.1/lake_id_geometries/lake_id_geom.csv https://minio-ad4gd-console.dashboard-siba.store/browser/pilot.1/lake_id_geometries/lake_id_bbox.csv
Dataset Links	https://fbinter.stadt-berlin.de/fb/atom/Gewaesserkarte/Gewaesserkarte.zip
Data Ownership	Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt oeffentlichkeitsarbeit@senmvku.berlin.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Surface water conductivity in river Spree, 2016

Dataset(s) description	Conductivity sensor (Probe AquaTroll 100) during summer 2016, installed close to Weidendammer Brücke at river Spree in the Berlin City Center. Time interval of measurements is 15 min. Besides Conductivity, the water temperature is measured, too. Suspended solids is calculated based on conductivity measurements.
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Conductivity, Water temperature, Surface Water, River, Combined Sewer Overflow, Urban Water Cycle
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/srv/api/records/9c316b30-0d8f-4553-bc4c-0b5d28eecdfe/attachments/Weid_Aqua100Data.csv

Data Ownership	Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin gGmbH malte.zamzow@kompetenz-wasser.de
Country of Origin	Germany
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

3.2.2 PILOT 2

Similarly, this section presents the consolidated overview of the datasets made available in the context of Pilot 2.

Table 9: Pilot 2 Datasets.

Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia – 2022

Dataset(s) description	Land use and land cover cartography of Catalonia for the year 2022 obtained through automatic classification of Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-2B images with a spatial resolution of 10 m and auxiliary information provided by the Generalitat de Catalunya from the Urban Map of Catalonia (https://territori.gencat.cat/ca/06_territori_i_urbanisme/observatori_territori/map_a_urbanistic_de_catalunya/) and the Road Graph (https://territori.gencat.cat/ca/01_departament/12_cartografia_i_toponimia/bases_cartografiques/infraestructures_mobilitat/infraestructures_terrestres/graf_infraestructures_terrestres) of the Department of Territory, as well as the Forest Fire Cartographic Base (https://agricultura.gencat.cat/ca/serveis/cartografia-sig/bases-cartografiques/boscoss/incendis-forestals) of the Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda and the lidar data from the Cartographic and Geological Institute of Catalonia (ICGC) (https://www.icgc.cat/Administracio-i-empresa/Descarregues/Elevacions/Dades-lidar).
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Catalunya
Data format	JSON
Dataset Links	https://agricultura.gencat.cat/ca/serveis/cartografia-sig/bases-cartografiques/usos-sol-subsol/usos-sol/
Data Ownership	Generalitat de Catalunya Grup de Recerca en Teledetecció i Sistemes d'Informació Geogràfica [Grumets, CREA-F-UAB]/ https://www.grumets.cat/
Country of Origin	Spain
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia

Dataset(s) description	The Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia is obtained through automatic classification of Landsat and Sentinel-2 images with a spatial resolution of 30 m and 10 m, with auxiliary information provided by the Generalitat de Catalunya. A specific methodology was applied to improve the temporal consistency of the entire MUCSC series.
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Land use, land cover, Remote Sensing, cartography (maps), Catalunya
Data format	JSON
Dataset Links	https://agricultura.gencat.cat/ca/serveis/cartografia-sig/bases-cartografiques/usos-sol-subsol/usos-sol/
Data Ownership	Generalitat de Catalunya Grup de Recerca en Teledetecció i Sistemes d'Informació Geogràfica [Grumets, CREA-F-UAB]/ https://www.grumets.cat/
Country of Origin	Spain
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia, enriched with OSM

Dataset(s) description	Additional preprocessing of The Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia carried out using Open Street Map data. The Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia is obtained through automatic classification of Landsat and Sentinel-2 images with a spatial resolution of 30 m and 10 m, with auxiliary information provided by the Generalitat de Catalunya. A specific methodology was applied to improve the temporal consistency of the entire MUCSC series.
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Remote Sensing, cartography (maps), land cover, Land Use
Data format	JSON
Data Ownership	Aston University https://www.aston.ac.uk/ Catalunya
Country of Origin	Spain
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Interaction Flow (IF) index

Dataset(s) description	Connectivity of habitats of rare and endangered species in Catalonia obtained through land-use/land-cover maps (LULC) processing via Graphab open-access software and based on MUCSC data for Catalonia and expert-defined values of habitat suitability (maximum distance for indefinite species to migrate - 600 meters from forest habitat patches).
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Connectivity, Terrestrial habitat connectivity, Remote Sensing, cartography (maps), Catalunya

Data format	DFDs
Dataset Links	https://sourcesup.renater.fr/www/graphab/en/home.html
Data Ownership	Aston University
Country of Origin	Spain
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Camera trap pictures and occurrences

Dataset(s) description	Preliminary data of camera tram observations in Catalonia. It contains the original references to pictures as well as the occurrences observations.
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Biodiversity, Camera trap, Connectivity, Mining concessions, Geoessential, IPR
Data format	JSON
Dataset Links	https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/ObservedProperties(58)/Datastreams(35)/Observations?\$expand=Datastream(\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\$expand=ObservedProperty(\$select=definition)),FeatureOfInterest(\$select=feature)###https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/ObservedProperties(59)/Datastreams(36)/Observations?\$expand=Datastream(\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\$expand=ObservedProperty(\$select=definition)),FeatureOfInterest(\$select=feature)###https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings3/v1.1/ObservedProperties(58)/Datastreams(35)/Observations?\$expand=ObservationGroups(\$expand=Observations),Datastream(\$select=unitOfMeasurement;\$expand=ObservedProperty(\$select=definition))
Data Ownership	CREAF i.serral@creaf.cat CREAF b.giralt@creaf.uab.cat
Country of Origin	Spain
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Mammals occurrences GBIF

Dataset(s) description	Subset query performed on 23/10/2023 on GBIF mammals occurrences data on the overall 2017 year.
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Mammals, GBIF, Occurrence
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/api/records/63a296c5-f132-4174-bac5-babe5ad94f2a/attachments/GBIF_Mammals_ANSI.csv
Data Ownership	CREAF ivette@creaf.cat
Restrictions on the use	Copyright
Country of Origin	Spain
Findability and Access	Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the

Access GeoNetwork in all cases.

Habitat corridors

Dataset(s) description Tif data with one band reflecting the number of forest habitat corridors intersecting each pixel derived from computations in Graphab software (maximum distance = 250 m) with additional processing steps (cropping raster data by buffer of 30 km from Catalonia border and compression to Cloud Optimised Geotiff, LZW)

Personal Data No

Purpose Habitat (Ecology), Habitats and biotopes, wildlife habitat, habitat

Data format Tif

Dataset Links <https://sourcesup.renater.fr/www/graphab/en/home.html>

Data Ownership Aston University kriukovv@aston.ac.uk

Country of Origin Spain

Findability and Access Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

Terrestrial Connectivity Index (ICT)

Dataset(s) description ICT approach to the Mediterranean landscape in which habitat types are not independent each other units but supporting frequent exchanges of terrestrial organisms and processes between them. This ICT calculation considers affinity and impedances values between habitat types, which modulate the weight of the habitat patch area. Values express the connectivity expressed as the log10 for each ha. Greater values of the index express better connectivity for that specific habitat.

Personal Data No

Purpose habitat loss and fragmentation, EBV Connectivity of terrestrial ecosystem habitat types

Data format GeoTIFF

Dataset Links <https://www.datacube.cat/BioConn/ICT/>
<https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py/collections/TerrestrialConnectivityIndex/coverage>

Data Ownership Generalitat de Catalunya
Grup de Recerca en Teledetecció i Sistemes d'Informació Geogràfica [Grumets, CREAL-UAB] contacte@creaf.uab.cat

Country of Origin Spain

Findability and Access Data access methods are provided by GeoNetwork. The discovery is done by the GeoNetwork in all cases.

3.2.3 PILOT 3

Finally, the present section presents the overview of the datasets within Pilot 3 catalogued in the GeoNetwork. Other results were uploaded and documented in the recently-developed Cross Data Store (XDS)¹⁸ in the ECMWF facilities directed.

Table 10: Pilot 3 Datasets.

PurpleAir Outdoor Sensor Air Quality Data Sample for AD4GD (Sensor ID 5428)

Dataset(s) description	This sample data file was downloaded from PurpleAir data provider. The CSV file contains data for outdoor air quality sensor (sensor ID 5428) for 1 day (2023-10-22) aggregated to 30-minute average. Latitude and Longitude data fields are not available for historic data. Available data fields: time_stamp rssi uptime pa_latency memory humidity humidity_a humidity_b temperature temperature_a temperature_b pressure pressure_a pressure_b voc voc_a voc_b analog_input pm2.5_alt pm2.5_alt_a pm2.5_alt_b scattering_coefficient scattering_coefficient_a scattering_coefficient_b deciviews deciviews_a deciviews_b visual_range visual_range_a visual_range_b 0.3_um_count 0.3_um_count_a 0.3_um_count_b 0.5_um_count 0.5_um_count_a 0.5_um_count_b 1.0_um_count 1.0_um_count_a 1.0_um_count_b 2.5_um_count 2.5_um_count_a 2.5_um_count_b 5.0_um_count 5.0_um_count_a 5.0_um_count_b 10.0_um_count 10.0_um_count_a 10.0_um_count_b pm1.0_cf_1 pm1.0_cf_1_a pm1.0_cf_1_b pm1.0_atm pm1.0_atm_a pm1.0_atm_b pm2.5_atm pm2.5_atm_a pm2.5_atm_b pm2.5_cf_1 pm2.5_cf_1_a pm2.5_cf_1_b pm10.0_atm pm10.0_atm_a pm10.0_atm_b pm10.0_cf_1 pm10.0_cf_1_a pm10.0_cf_1_b
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Outdoor air quality sensor (sensor ID 5428) for 1 day (2023-10-22) aggregated to 30-minute average
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/srv/api/records/f14ec4da-dfb3-47a3-8ad8-7d44ea927e2b/attachments/5428%202023-10-22%202023-10-23%2030-Minute%20Average.csv
Data Ownership	Aston University test@aston.ac.uk
Country of Origin	UK
Restrictions on the use	<p>Before accessing our API, please be sure to read our Terms of Service (https://www.purpleair.com/terms). A few Terms of Service requirements to be aware of when using the PurpleAir API:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Grantback license (see Section 4.4 of the Terms of Service (https://www.purpleair.com/terms)) * Attribution (see Section 4.8 of the Terms of Service (https://www.purpleair.com/terms) and Attribution page (https://www.purpleair.com/attribution)) * Limited data distribution to one-level removed (see Section 4.3 of the Terms of Service (https://www.purpleair.com/terms)), i.e., a user of PurpleAir API can utilize PurpleAir data to provide to an end-user (e.g., a viewer of a map or user of an app),

¹⁸ <https://xds-dev.ecmwf.int/datasets/derived-air-quality>

but cannot resell data or an API modeled from PurpleAir data
* Fair Use Policy (see Exhibit A of the Terms of Service
(<https://www.purpleair.com/terms>))

Findability and Access

As above.

CAMS European air quality forecasts

Dataset(s) description

This dataset provides daily air quality analyses and forecasts for Europe. CAMS produces specific daily air quality analyses and forecasts for the European domain at significantly higher spatial resolution (0.1 degrees, approx. 10km) than is available from the global analyses and forecasts. The production is based on an ensemble of eleven air quality forecasting systems across Europe. A median ensemble is calculated from individual outputs, since ensemble products yield on average better performance than the individual model products. The spread between the eleven models are used to provide an estimate of the forecast uncertainty. The analysis combines model data with observations provided by the European Environment Agency (EEA) into a complete and consistent dataset using various data assimilation techniques depending upon the air-quality forecasting system used. In parallel, air quality forecasts are produced once a day for the next four days. Both the analysis and the forecast are available at hourly time steps and multiple height levels. Note that only nitrogen monoxide, nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide, ozone, PM2.5, PM10 and dust are regularly validated against in-situ observations, and therefore forecasts of all other variables are unvalidated and should be considered experimental.

Personal Data

No

Purpose

This dataset provides daily air quality analyses and forecasts for europe cams produces specific daily air quality analyses and forecasts for the european domain at significantly higher spatial resolution 0 1 degrees approx 10km than is available from the global analyses and forecasts the production is based on an ensemble of eleven air quality forecasting systems across europe a median ensemble is calculated from individual outputs since ensemble products yield on average better performance than the individual model products the spread between the eleven models are used to provide an estimate of the forecast uncertainty the analysis combines model data with observations provided by the european environment agency eea into a complete and consistent dataset using various data assimilation techniques depending upon the air-quality forecasting system used in parallel air quality forecasts are produced once a day for the next four days both the analysis and the forecast are available at hourly time steps and multiple height levels note that only nitrogen monoxide nitrogen dioxide sulphur dioxide ozone pm2 5 pm10 and dust are regularly validated against in-situ observations and therefore forecasts of all other variables are unvalidated and should be considered experimental alder pollen: units, grains m -3, ammonia: units, netcdf: -3, birch pollen: units, grains m 3, carbon monoxide: units, kg, m -3, netcdf: -3, formaldehyde: units, kg, m -3, netcdf, m -3, glyoxal: units, kg, m -3, netcdf, grass pollen: units, grains m -3, mugwort pollen: units: grains m, -3, nitrogen dioxide: units, kg m, -3,

netcdf: m, -3, nitrogen monoxide: units, kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, non-methane volatile organic compounds vocs : units, kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, olive pollen: units: grains m, -3, ozone: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, pm10 dust: units, kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, pm10 sea salt dry : units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, pm10 wildfires: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, pm2 5 ammonium: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, pm2 5 nitrate: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, pm2 5 residential elementary carbon: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, pm2 5 secondary inorganic aerosol: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, pm2 5 sulphate: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, pm2 5 total elementary carbon: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, pm2 5 total organic matter: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, particulate matter < 10, pm10 : units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, particulate matter < 2 5, pm2 5 : units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, peroxyacyl nitrates: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3, ragweed pollen: units: grains m, -3, sulphur dioxide: units: kg m, -3, netcdf: m, -3

Country of Origin

EU

CAMS European air quality reanalyses**Dataset(s) description**

This dataset provides annual air quality reanalyses for Europe based on both unvalidated and validated observations. CAMS produces annual air quality reanalyses for the European domain at significantly higher spatial resolution (0.1 degrees, approx. 10km) than is available from the global reanalyses. The production is currently based on an ensemble of eleven air quality data assimilation systems across Europe. A median ensemble is calculated from individual outputs, since ensemble products yield on average better performance than the individual model products. The spread between the eleven models can be used to provide an estimate of the analysis uncertainty. The reanalysis combines model data with observations provided by the European Environment Agency (EEA) into a complete and consistent dataset using various data assimilation techniques depending upon the air-quality forecasting system used. Additional sources of observations can complement the in-situ data assimilation, like satellite data. An interim reanalysis is provided each year for the year before based on the unvalidated near-real-time observation data stream that had not undergone full quality control by the data providers yet. Once the fully quality-controlled observations are available from the data provider, typically with an additional delay of about 1 year, a final validated annual reanalysis is provided. Both reanalyses are available at hourly time steps at height levels.

Personal Data

No

Purpose

This dataset provides annual air quality reanalyses for europe based on both unvalidated and validated observations cams produces annual air quality reanalyses for the european domain at significantly higher spatial resolution 0 1 degrees approx 10km than is available from the global reanalyses the production is currently based on an ensemble of eleven air quality data assimilation systems across europe a median ensemble is calculated from individual outputs since ensemble products yield on average better performance than the individual model products the spread between the eleven models can be used to provide an estimate of the analysis uncertainty the reanalysis combines model data with observations provided by the european environment agency eea into a complete and consistent dataset using various data assimilation techniques depending upon the air-quality

forecasting system used additional sources of observations can complement the in-situ data assimilation like satellite data an **interim** reanalysis is provided each year for the year before based on the unvalidated near-real-time observation data stream that had not undergone full quality control by the data providers yet once the fully quality-controlled observations are available from the data provider typically with an additional delay of about 1 year a final **validated** annual reanalysis is provided both reanalyses are available at hourly time steps at height levels main variables: ammonia: units, carbon monoxide: units, formaldehyde: units, glyoxal: units, nitrogen dioxide: units, nitrogen monoxide: units, non-methane volatile organic compounds vocs : units, ozone: units, pm10 dust: units, pm10 sea salt dry : units, pm10 wildfires: units, pm2 5 residential elementary carbon: units, pm2 5 secondary inorganic aerosol: units, pm2 5 total elementary carbon: units, pm2 5 total organic matter: units, particulate matter, pm10 : units, particulate matter : units, peroxyacyl nitrates: units, sulphur dioxide: units

PurpleAir Indoor Sensor Air Quality Data Sample for AD4GD (Sensor ID 157047)

Dataset(s) description	This sample data file was downloaded from PurpleAir data provider. The CSV file contains data for indoor air quality sensor (sensor ID 157047) for 1 day (2023-10-22) aggregated to 30-minute average. Latitude and Longitude data fields are not available for historic data. Available data fields: time_stamp rssi uptime pa_latency memory humidity humidity_a humidity_b temperature temperature_a temperature_b pressure pressure_a pressure_b voc voc_a voc_b analog_input pm2.5_alt pm2.5_alt_a pm2.5_alt_b scattering_coefficient scattering_coefficient_a scattering_coefficient_b deciviews deciviews_a deciviews_b visual_range visual_range_a visual_range_b 0.3_um_count 0.3_um_count_a 0.3_um_count_b 0.5_um_count 0.5_um_count_a 0.5_um_count_b 1.0_um_count 1.0_um_count_a 1.0_um_count_b 2.5_um_count 2.5_um_count_a 2.5_um_count_b 5.0_um_count 5.0_um_count_a 5.0_um_count_b 10.0_um_count 10.0_um_count_a 10.0_um_count_b pm1.0_cf_1 pm1.0_cf_1_a pm1.0_cf_1_b pm1.0_atm pm1.0_atm_a pm1.0_atm_b pm2.5_atm pm2.5_atm_a pm2.5_atm_b pm2.5_cf_1 pm2.5_cf_1_a pm2.5_cf_1_b pm10.0_atm pm10.0_atm_a pm10.0_atm_b pm10.0_cf_1 pm10.0_cf_1_a pm10.0_cf_1_b
Personal Data	No
Purpose	Indoor air quality sensor (sensor ID 157047) for 1 day (2023-10-22) aggregated to 30-minute average.
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.edit
Data Ownership	Aston University test@aston.ac.uk
Country of Origin	UK
Restrictions on the use	Before accessing our API, please be sure to read our Terms of Service (https://www.purpleair.com/terms). A few Terms of Service requirements to be aware of when using the PurpleAir API: * Grantback license (see Section 4.4 of the Terms of Service (https://www.purpleair.com/terms)) * Attribution (see Section 4.8 of the Terms of Service

(<https://www.purpleair.com/terms>) and Attribution page (<https://www.purpleair.com/attribution>)

* Limited data distribution to one-level removed (see Section 4.3 of the Terms of Service (<https://www.purpleair.com/terms>)), i.e., a user of PurpleAir API can utilize PurpleAir data to provide to an end-user (e.g., a viewer of a map or user of an app), but cannot resell data or an API modeled from PurpleAir data

* Fair Use Policy (see Exhibit A of the Terms of Service (<https://www.purpleair.com/terms>))

Sensor.Community Air Quality Data

Dataset(s) description	<p>Sensor.Community is an open source citizen science project collecting various types of environment information. Useful links Main landing page: https://sensor.community/ User community forum: https://forum.sensor.community/ Sensor.Community Data License: https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/dbcl/1-0/ Official API documentation: https://github.com/opendata-stuttgart/meta/wiki/EN-APIs Unofficial documentation: https://api-sensor-community.bessarabov.com/ Measurement Types Meteorological data: Air temperature (in °C), Air pressure (in Pa), Relative humidity (in %), Air quality data: Particulate matter: PM1, PM2.5, PM10 (in µg/m3), nitrogen oxides: NO, NO2 (tbd), Noise measurements. Data Sources: Daily CSV files broken down by sensor can be downloaded from https://archive.sensor.community. Monthly bundled csv files are also available from https://archive.sensor.community/csv_per_month/ Grafana API - InfluxDB, query real-time data: https://api-rrd.madavi.de:3000/grafana/api/datasources/proxy/uid/hoUeJn4Gz/query Location data stored as 9-character precision geohash</p>
Personal Data	No
Purpose	To measure and review air quality.
Data format	CSV
Dataset Links	https://sensor.community/en/
Data Ownership	Sensor.Community contact@sensor.community

ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present

Dataset(s) description	<p>ERA5 is the fifth generation ECMWF reanalysis for the global climate and weather for the past 8 decades. Data is available from 1940 onwards. ERA5 replaces the ERA-Interim reanalysis. Reanalysis combines model data with observations from across the world into a globally complete and consistent dataset using the laws of physics. This principle, called data assimilation, is based on the method used by numerical weather prediction centres, where every so many hours (12 hours at ECMWF) a previous forecast is combined with newly available observations in an optimal way to produce a new best estimate of the state of the atmosphere, called analysis, from which an updated, improved forecast is issued. Reanalysis works in the same way, but at reduced resolution to allow for the provision of a dataset spanning back several decades. Reanalysis does not have the constraint of issuing timely forecasts, so there is more time to collect observations, and when going</p>
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further back in time, to allow for the ingestion of improved versions of the original observations, which all benefit the quality of the reanalysis product. ERA5 provides hourly estimates for a large number of atmospheric, ocean-wave and land-surface quantities. An uncertainty estimate is sampled by an underlying 10-member ensemble at three-hourly intervals. Ensemble mean and spread were pre-computed for convenience. Such uncertainty estimates are closely related to the information content of the available observing system which evolved considerably over time. They also indicate flow-dependent sensitive areas. To facilitate many climate applications, monthly-mean averages were pre-calculated too, though monthly means are not available for the ensemble mean and spread. ERA5 is updated daily with a latency of about 5 days. In case that serious flaws are detected in this early release (called ERA5T), this data could be different from the final release 2 to 3 months later. In case that this occurs users are notified. The data set presented here is a regridded subset of the full ERA5 data set on native resolution. It is online on spinning disk, which should ensure fast and easy access. It should satisfy the requirements for most common applications. An overview of all ERA5 datasets can be found in this article. Information on access to ERA5 data on native resolution is provided in these guidelines. Data was regridded to a regular lat-lon grid of 0.25 degrees for the reanalysis and 0.5 degrees for the uncertainty estimate (0.5 and 1 degree respectively for ocean waves). There are four main sub sets: hourly and monthly products, both on pressure levels (upper air fields) and single levels (atmospheric, ocean-wave and land surface quantities). The present entry is \ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present\".

Personal Data	No
Purpose	Reanalysis, Past, Global, Atmosphere (surface), Atmosphere (upper air), Copernicus C3S, air temperature, dew point temperature, air pressure at mean sea level, atmosphere boundary layer thickness
Data format	Unknown
Dataset Links	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47
Data Ownership	ECMWF https://support.ecmwf.int

4 GEOSS PRINCIPLES OF DATA MANAGEMENT AND DATA SHARING

In order to best align the project's activities with the Open Science principle, AD4GD was considered the complementary guiding principles provided by the Group on Earth Observations with regards to data management¹⁹ and data sharing²⁰.

As such, as far as **data management** is concerned, the Consortium took into account the following aspects, as detailed in the section above:

1. **Discoverability**, making the data findable;
2. **Accessibility**;
3. **Usability**;
4. **Preservation**, requiring that data remains protected from loss and is preserved for future use, in accordance with a preservation plan that will also ensure that integrity, authenticity and readability is verified for both data and metadata;
5. **Curation**, ensuring that corrections, updates, and reprocessing are possible, while enabling citations of data based on persistent and resolvable identifiers.

Similarly, the GEO formulated the following **data sharing principles**, promoting:

1. **Full and open exchange** of data, metadata and products shared withing GEOSS;
2. Availability of all shared data, metadata, and products **with minimum time delay and at minimum cost**;
3. Availability of all shared data, metadata, and products **free of charge or at a cost no more than the cost of reproduction for research and education purposes**.

AD4GD not only considered the above-described principles but it also incorporated them as much as possible to its activities and architecture, while respecting legal and ethical requirements.

¹⁹ GEO Data Management Principles Task Force, 'GEOSS Data Management Principles' (28 April 2015).

²⁰ Data Sharing Working Group of the Group on Earth Observations, 'GEOSS Data Sharing Principles post 2015' (10 March 2014).

5 ETHICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS

The present sections summarises the ethical and legal requirements that were identified as relevant to the project's activities and thus shaped its course of action. Similarly, it presents the related compliance activities at the project level and the tools developed to further enhance it.

5.1 AD4GD MANAGEMENT OF COMPLIANCE ACTIVITIES

The main technical and implementation components of the project were divided into individual work packages and allocated to task leaders, according to their intended purpose and expected outputs. The figure below provides a high-level overview of the distribution of responsibilities and tasks among the different work packages.

Figure 7: Workplan structure and interactions

In addition to the above, Articles 37-39 GDPR define the role of the Data Protection Officer, a figure distinguished for their expert knowledge of data protection law and practices. The DPO is, generally, in charge of monitoring the application of the GDPR within an organisation, while informing and advising controllers on how to comply with obligations stemming from the applicable data protection provisions.

As such, and to ensure compliance with the relevant data protection legislation, AD4GD, in the context of Task 8.3, appointed a **DPO for the project, namely ECCP**, who took care of:

- **Coordinating with the respective DPOs of the data controllers** involved in the project;
- **Overviewing the project's compliance** with the GDPR (where personal data processing is involved) and other current and upcoming regulatory obligations;
- **Periodically reporting on the project's compliance** with applicable data protection norms in the course of project development;
- **Providing recommendations**, where applicable, to partners regarding their data management strategy within the project.

5.2 ETHICAL PRINCIPLES AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

AD4GD was committed to adhering to ethical and legal standards, regulations and principles in all activities related to the project. Compliance with key ethical principles include:

Data Usage: Personal data was not sold or used outside the AD4GD project's objectives. Any additional personal data inadvertently collected was promptly erased, with only relevant data being collected and anonymized as needed.

Data Disclosure: Personal data was not shared beyond the project's scope and any data sharing within the project will be governed by legal requirements and formal agreements that outline the roles, rights, and obligations of all partners.

Participant Privacy: For activities involving human participants (e.g. surveys), measures will be taken to ensure privacy, confidentiality, and non-discrimination.

Publication: Personal data was not disclosed in publications or dissemination activities, with anonymization techniques and aggregated data used instead.

No ethical or legal concerns affecting data sharing were identified by the partners.

The ethical and regulatory framework that shaped the project's activities is detailed in previous iterations of this deliverable and is summarised in the table below:

Table 11: Summary of Ethical and Legal Framework of relevance for AD4GD.

Ethical Instrument	Description	Relevance for AD4GD
Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI	These guidelines ensure that AI development aligns with the European Union's Charter of Fundamental Rights and other relevant international human rights standards.	Development and implementation of AI and Machine Learning techniques and tools.
AI Act	A unified legal framework for AI development, deployment, and use across the EU.	Use of advanced AI techniques, including Deep Learning, from the shared Dataspace for Earth Observation to enhance data quality, ensure interoperability, data fusion and harmony from heterogenous information from diverse sources.
General Data Protection Regulation	Requirements on ensuring personal data protection and data subjects' rights.	Potential of incidental collection of personal data during geo-location data collection.
ePrivacy Directive	Regulation of the use of cookies in websites and an initial view of the data protection and privacy provisions in the sector of electronic communications.	Data processing, including in the AD4GD public resources and repositories.
Data Governance Act	Supporting the creation and development of European Dataspaces leveraging on the collaboration between private and public players, in sectors such as health, environment, energy, agriculture, mobility, finance, manufacturing, public administration and skills.	Project's role in the establishment of the European GDDS and the DGA's objective of increasing data availability, building trust in data sharing and overcoming technical obstacles to the reuse of data.
Data Act	Definition of the actors who can create value from data and under which	Project's deployment of IoT devices to collect data and reusability of collected

	conditions, in particular with regard to the data generated by IoT devices.	datasets.
Database Directive ²¹	Requirements for the enrichment and fusion of existing datasets which are currently created and managed within different silos.	Generation of AD4GD datasets for tests and validation of data integration and its semantic interoperability space.
Open Data Directive ²²	Minimum rules on the re-use of data held by the public sector and of publicly funded research data made freely accessible through repositories	Use of open data sets (e.g., GeoNetwork), leveraging the European Open Science Cloud infrastructure and its extensive collection of data.
Regulation on the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data ²³	Rules to foster the free movement of non-personal data across EU countries and IT systems in Europe.	Collection, processing and generation of non-personal data.
NIS Directives ²⁴	Cybersecurity rules aiming at achieving a high common level of cybersecurity across the Member States.	Need to ensure the cybersecurity of AD4GD datasets, tools and solutions.

5.3 COMPLIANCE CRITERIA FOR EARTH OBSERVATION DATA

In addition to the above-described activities, and in order to further enhance the project's compliance framework, the development of a dedicated set of criteria to assess the compliance of collecting, processing and sharing earth observation data was proposed.

As a first step towards this procedure, the most relevant legislative and normative documents were identified and analysed so as to conclude to the following list:

1. The Outer Space Treaty²⁵;
2. The Rescue Agreement²⁶;
3. The Space Liability Convention²⁷;
4. The Registration Convention²⁸;
5. The Moon Agreement²⁹;

²¹ Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases [1996] OJ L 077/20.

²² European Parliament and Council of the European Union, "Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on Open Data and the Re-Use of Public Sector Information," June 20, 2019, <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj/eng>, [Last accessed 27 February 2023].

²³ Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union [2018] OJ L 303/59.

²⁴ Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union [2016] OJ L 194/1.

²⁵ <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>

²⁶ <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introrescueagreement.html>

²⁷ <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introliability-convention.html>

²⁸ <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/registration-convention.html>

6. The UN Charter³⁰;
7. The ITU Radio Regulations³¹;
8. The Broadcasting Convention³²;
9. The Principles Relating to Remote Sensing of the Earth from Outer Space, General Assembly resolution 41/65 of 3 December 1986³³;
10. The GDPR;
11. The AI Act;
12. The Data Act;
13. The Data Governance Act.

On the basis of the above, an initial mapping of requirements was performed and, subsequently, a set of criteria were developed to assist interested parties not only within but also beyond the Consortium to assess compliance of their earth observation data-related activities with the identified obligations. It is worth highlighting that although many of the above documents primarily refer to States' obligations, the mapping and analysis process ensured that only the requirements related to private entities were extracted and utilised for the criteria development phase.

Leveraging on the Europrivacy³⁴ approach (the first Data Protection Seal pursuant to the GDPR), the criteria adopted a similar methodology and structure, meaning each criterion is followed by:

- A unique reference identifier;
- A short title describing the criterion content;
- The criterion itself;
- Implementing guidance to assist interested parties in understanding how the criterion is to be applied and reviewed;
- Suggested means of verification, to further help with comprehending the evidence that may be used to demonstrate compliance with the criterion's requirements;
- The legal reference, so that the corresponding legal and normative obligation is clearly defined.

All of the above elements ensure that interested parties can easily comprehend and assess their obligations derived from the above documents and ensuring compliance. Simultaneously, third-party audit and assessment can take place by qualified official auditors³⁵ who can then certify said compliance.

The criteria were submitted to the Europrivacy International Board of Experts for further review and formal adoption, so their exploitation is further pursued through the work of the European Centre for

²⁹ <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/intromoon-agreement.html>

³⁰ <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/un-charter/full-text>

³¹ <https://www.itu.int/pub/R-REG-RR>

³² <https://docs.pca-cpa.org/2016/01/International-Convention-concerning-the-Use-of-Broadcasting-in-the-Cause-of-Peace-1936.pdf>

³³ https://www.unoosa.org/pdf/gares/ARES_41_65E.pdf

³⁴ <https://europrivacy.com/>

³⁵ <https://europrivacy.com/en/partners/list>

Certification and Privacy (ECCP). Once formally validated, they will be made available at the Europrivacy Community Website (community.europrivacy.com).

6 PUBLICATIONS AND IPR GUIDELINES

AD4GD generated a range of data, tools and knowledge, some of which might be confidential and some of which will be for dissemination and communication to the public. IPR, within this context, takes into account any IPR including, but not limited to, copyright, patents, trademarks, trade secrets, and database rights. As such, it is the **Consortium Agreement that primarily lays down the foundation for the IPR Policy, identifying Background IPR brought by partners to the project and** providing the general framework regarding, among the others, the following points:

- a) The **procedure to exercise partners' right to object to dissemination**;
- b) The **procedure of making research outputs available** to larger scientific and research communities or peer-reviewed publications only by its proprietors or through authorisation;
- c) An **assessment of the background knowledge of project partners**, their potential contribution to the creation of foreground IP, and potential IP overlap;
- d) The **partners' agreement to grant the consortium with Access Rights to necessary background knowledge** for the successful execution of the project, including the conditions for sublicensing, where desired;
- e) The **protection of confidential information** that may be leveraged on but not published;
- f) The **wide dissemination of non-sensitive and not reserved for exploitation knowledge** with the EC open access policy;
- g) The **further use, development and exploitation of portable software components** developed in the context of the project by the consortium members;
- h) The **results of the termination of a partner's participation** on its obligation to grant access rights to other partners until the end of the project.

Pre-developed IPR brought into the project by partners remain their own property and are not affected by their participation to AD4GD. Where IPR owned by a third party was brought into the project, the partner introducing it ensured that they possessed the required legalization documents for their use, including licenses.

Similarly, **IPR that was generated in the context of the project are by default owned by the partner who developed the innovation or content.** Where more partners participated in the development of the same IPR, they are required to sign a written agreement where their respective rights and obligations will be thoroughly described. Such agreement may also include the terms and conditions of IPR exploitation.

The AD4GD project's ownership strategy was deliberately crafted to safeguard the long-term sustainability of its outcomes and to enable a seamless legal transfer of results. This approach is rooted in the Consortium Agreement, transparent licensing frameworks, and thoughtful institutional transitions (from Ad4DG project consortium to SAGE, the next EU project), all aimed at maximizing the project's lasting impact.

In line with the Open Science and FAIR data principles, the project prioritised open access to its datasets, products and/or solutions, as defined by the project, aiming at outcomes that are open, standard-based and will prevent vendor lock-in to the greater extent possible and in balance with the partners' IPR generated in the context of the project. In line with this commitment, and as reported in the exploitation strategy defined in *D7.4 – GDDS Exploitation Perspectives*, the project aimed to not pursue any patents or similar

IPR, but to make its results openly available on the basis of licenses. More information on these aspects are provided in D7.4.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The data collected and produced by AD4GD is in compliance with the Open Science and FAIR principles, ethics and legal provisions. This document demonstrates the compliance of the data produced by the project within the Pilots, to the FAIR principles, as well as legal and normative requirements.

This document focuses on reporting the achievements in data management aspects in AD4GD through demonstrating that a GeoNetwork catalogue provides discoverability of all data in the project; the distribution aspects on the metadata in GeoNetwork ensures data access; and the tools for data semantics (included the GDIM) improved interoperability and cross-domain activities. All datasets in GeoNetwork has a clearly defined license that ensures re-usability of the dataset produced in the Pilots and beyond. In conclusion, the data management plans at the beginning of the project were transformed into practical actions that implemented the plans into all datasets produced and managed by AD4GD.

Considering the sustainability aspects of data management beyond the project's duration, the current DMP is fully aligned with the exploitation strategy, as the analysis of the project's overall results demonstrates. In this regard, the DMP extends the previously DMP versions and enriches it with the long-term preservation and reuse of the data and other results, focusing particularly on the overall approach towards data management and with FAIR and Open Science Principles.

Through data integration, the Pilot data availability improved and trust was build in data sharing. The integration helped to overcome technical obstacles in line with the priorities of biodiversity, air pollution and water quality based on sustainable data governance with the purpose of benefiting the GDDS.

Finally, the IPR strategy is summarised, highlighting the project's commitment to Open Science, opting for open licences instead of a closed system of IPR protection, to promote reusability and further dissemination of its results well beyond the project's duration.

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